

Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of Schiff bases derived from fluoroaminothiazole : spectral, magnetic and biological studies

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Manuscript received 26 April 2010, revised 29 September 2010, accepted 05 October 2010

Abstract : Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of Schiff bases derived from 4-(*p*-fluorophenyl)-2-aminothiazole and *o*-hydroxyaldehydes (substituted salicylaldehyde, *o*-vanillin and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde) have been synthesized. The complexes were characterized by elemental (C, H, N and metal) and spectral (UV-Visible and IR) analyses, magnetic susceptibility and conductivity measurements and evaluation of biological activities. The complexes possess 1 : 2 metal : ligand stoichiometry (ML₂) and an octahedral geometry. Various ligand field parameters (*B*, *Dq*, β , *F*₂ and *F*₄, *F*² and *F*⁴, ν_3/ν_1 , ν_2/ν_1 , ν_3/ν_2 and *Dq/B* etc.) for Co^{II} complexes have been calculated. The complexes exhibit enhanced antibacterial and antifungal activity as compared to the parent ligands. This phenomenon is explained on the grounds of Overtone's concept and chelation theory.

Keywords : Co^{II} complexes, Zn^{II} complexes, Schiff base metal complexes.

Introduction

Schiff bases obtained from *o*-hydroxyaldehydes possess a strong ability to form metal complexes. A number of reviews¹ have been devoted to coordination chemistry, which throws light on synthesis and characterization of Schiff base metal complexes. Thiazoles are well known as biologically active ligands and they exhibit a wide range of antitubercular², antibacterial³, antifungal⁴, and hypotensive and hypodermic⁵ activities. Disubstituted thiazoles possess anti-inflammatory and analgesic⁶ activities. The Schiff bases derived from aminothiazoles and their transition metal complexes are expected to be biologically active compounds. In our earlier communication, we have reported spectral, thermal, XRD and biological studies on 4-(*p*-fluorophenyl)-2-aminothiazole⁷.

In this communication we report synthesis and characterization of Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of Schiff bases (LH) (Fig. 1) obtained by reacting 4-(*p*-fluorophenyl)-2-aminothiazole and *o*-hydroxyaldehydes (substituted salicylaldehyde, *o*-vanillin and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde). The ligands and their complexes have been characterized by elemental and spectral analyses and evaluation of antibacterial and antifungal activities. The magnetic susceptibility values of the complexes were also reported.

Fig. 1

Results and discussion

Schiff bases :

The Schiff bases (LH-1 to LH-8) are yellow crystalline solids having sharp melting points. They are soluble in common organic solvents (ethanol, acetone, chloroform and DMF etc.) and gave satisfactory elemental (C, H and N) analyses. The elemental analyses and melting point data is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Elemental analyses and melting point data of Schiff bases

Sl. no.	Schiff base	R	Calcd. (Found) (%)			M.p. (°C)
			C	H	N	
1.	LH-1	H	64.43 (64.22)	3.69 (3.55)	9.39 (9.38)	158
2.	LH-2	3-CH ₃	65.38 (65.27)	4.17 (4.16)	8.97 (8.90)	135
3.	LH-3	4-CH ₃	65.38 (65.36)	4.17 (4.18)	8.97 (8.91)	176
4.	LH-4	5-CH ₃	65.38 (65.37)	4.17 (4.15)	8.97 (8.89)	175
5.	LH-5	5-Cl	57.74 (57.71)	3.00 (2.89)	8.42 (8.40)	185
6.	LH-6	5-Br	50.93 (50.88)	2.65 (2.61)	7.43 (7.38)	169
7.	LH-7	3-OCH ₃	62.20 (62.21)	3.96 (3.91)	8.54 (8.51)	158
8.	LH-8		68.97 (68.94)	3.74 (3.69)	8.04 (7.99)	176

UV-Visible spectra of Schiff bases in chloroform exhibit an intense band at ~400 nm. UV-Visible spectrum of 4-(*p*-fluorophenyl)-2-aminothiazole exhibits an intense band at ~300 nm. 2-Aminothiazole absorbs at ~275 nm whereas other aromatic amino compounds with comparable structures exhibit absorption⁸ at ~300 nm. The shifting of absorption band towards higher wavelength (~400 nm) in the present Schiff bases may be due to extended conjugation in the molecule⁹.

Infrared spectra of the Schiff bases exhibit $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$, $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-S-C}}$ modes at ~3400, ~1630, ~1280 and ~665 cm^{-1} respectively and these values are in accordance with the earlier reported data¹⁰. ν_{OH} mode is broad and weak and this may be due to hydrogen bonding between phenolic -OH and nitrogen of the azomethine group¹⁰.

¹H NMR data of the Schiff bases is represented below. The assignments of NMR signals show close resemblance with the earlier results¹¹.

NMR signals (δ ppm) :

LH-1 : 7.25 (1H, s, thiazole), 7.02–7.89 (8H, m, Ar-H), 9.26 (1H, s, benzylidenimin), 12.08 (1H, s, Ar-OH); LH-2 : 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.80 (1H, s, thiazole), 7.1–7.4 (7H, m, Ar-H), 9.26 (1H, s, benzylidenimin), 12.30 (1H, s, Ar-OH); LH-3 : 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.80–7.90 (8H, m,

thiazole and Ar-H), 9.26 (1H, s, benzylidenimin), 12.30 (1H, s, Ar-OH); LH-4 : 2.40 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.80–7.90 (8H, m, thiazole and Ar-H), 9.24 (1H, s, benzylidenimin), 12.08 (1H, s, Ar-OH); LH-5 : 6.98–7.49 (8H, m, thiazole and Ar-H), 9.26 (1H, s, benzylidenimin), 12.27 (1H, s, Ar-OH); LH-6 : 6.66–7.39 (8H, m, thiazole and Ar-H), 9.25 (1H, s, benzylidenimin), 12.29 (1H, s, Ar-OH); LH-7 : 3.96 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.99–7.95 (8H, m, thiazole and Ar-H), 9.33 (1H, s, benzylidenimin), 12.56 (1H, s, Ar-OH); LH-8 : 6.90–8.30 (11H, m, thiazole and Ar-H), 10.12 (1H, s, benzylidenimin), 14.33 (1H, s, Ar-OH).

The Schiff bases were tested for the evaluation of antibacterial activity against *K. pneumoniae* (Gram-negative bacterium) and *S. aureus* (Gram-positive bacterium) and antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *C. albicans* by serial dilution technique¹² in DMF in the concentration range 1–50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The MIC values lie in the range 12–16 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for antibacterial activity and 10–12 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for antifungal activity.

Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes :

The Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes are reddish brown and orange red colored shining crystalline solids respectively and melt with decomposition without showing sharp melting points above 220 °C. They are soluble in organic solvents like chloroform, nitrobenzene and DMF. The elemental analyses data (Table 2) suggested that complexes possess 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry. The very low molar conductance values ($< 10 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) in nitrobenzene solution and molecular weight determination data indicated that the complexes are nonelectrolytic and monomeric in nature.

Electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes exhibit bands at ~8600, ~18000, ~20000 and ~26000 cm^{-1} . Occurrence of first three bands, attributing to transitions ${}^4T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g} (\nu_1)$, ${}^4A_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4T_{2g} (\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g} (P) \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g} (\nu_3)$ respectively, suggested an octahedral geometry for the complexes. An intense band at ~26000 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon = 1000 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) may be due to ligand to metal (metal \leftarrow ligand) charge transfer¹⁴. Zn^{II} complexes show an intense band at ~26000 cm^{-1} , which may be due to ligand to metal (metal \leftarrow ligand) charge transfer¹⁴.

In order to calculate $10Dq$ and Racah parameter *B* values, König¹⁵ has summarized four fitting procedures for *d*⁷ cases : (a) fitting the first and second band, (b)

Table 2. Elemental analyses data of Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	R	Calcd. (Found) (%)				μ_{eff} (B.M.)
			C	H	N	M	
1.	CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-1)	H	58.81 (58.74)	3.06 (3.00)	8.57 (8.51)	9.02 (8.89)	4.90
2.	CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-2)	3-CH ₃	59.92 (59.87)	3.52 (3.51)	8.22 (8.19)	8.65 (8.62)	5.10
3.	CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-3)	4-CH ₃	59.92 (59.90)	3.52 (3.52)	8.22 (8.18)	8.65 (8.61)	4.90
4.	CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-4)	5-CH ₃	59.92 (59.88)	3.52 (3.49)	8.22 (8.20)	8.65 (8.60)	4.98
5.	CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-5)	5-Cl	53.19 (53.17)	2.49 (2.49)	7.75 (7.75)	8.15 (8.15)	4.85
6.	CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-6)	5-Br	47.36 (47.31)	2.22 (2.19)	6.90 (6.89)	7.26 (7.21)	4.80
7.	CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-7)	3-OCH ₃	57.23 (57.15)	3.37 (3.25)	7.86 (7.78)	8.26 (8.17)	4.95
8.	CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-8)		63.75 (63.70)	3.18 (3.17)	7.43 (7.41)	7.82 (7.79)	5.00
9.	ZnL ₂ (Ligand : LH-1)	H	58.23 (58.20)	3.03 (2.90)	8.49 (8.40)	9.91 (9.89)	Diamagnetic
10.	ZnL ₂ (Ligand : LH-2)	3-CH ₃	59.35 (59.30)	3.49 (3.38)	8.14 (8.00)	9.51 (9.45)	Diamagnetic
11.	ZnL ₂ (Ligand : LH-3)	4-CH ₃	59.35 (59.30)	3.49 (3.39)	8.14 (8.10)	9.51 (9.47)	Diamagnetic
12.	ZnL ₂ (Ligand : LH-4)	5-CH ₃	59.35 (59.31)	3.49 (3.39)	8.14 (8.00)	9.51 (9.48)	Diamagnetic
13.	ZnL ₂ (Ligand : LH-5)	5-Cl	52.72 (52.65)	2.47 (2.39)	7.69 (7.59)	8.98 (8.88)	Diamagnetic
14.	ZnL ₂ (Ligand : LH-6)	5-Br	46.98 (46.75)	2.20 (2.18)	6.85 (6.81)	8.00 (7.86)	Diamagnetic
15.	ZnL ₂ (Ligand : LH-7)	3-OCH ₃	56.71 (56.23)	3.33 (3.22)	7.78 (7.65)	9.00 (9.08)	Diamagnetic
16.	ZnL ₂ (Ligand : LH-8)		63.20 (63.10)	3.16 (3.17)	7.37 (7.26)	8.61 (8.50)	Diamagnetic

fitting the first and third band, (c) fitting the second and third band and (d) fitting the difference between the first and second band. Fitting procedure (d) is applicable when all *d-d* transitions are observed. In the present Co^{II} complexes, we have adopted fitting procedure (d) (eqs. 1 and 2) because all three *d-d* transition bands ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 are observed. The values of $10Dq$ and B are given in Table 3.

$$10Dq = \nu_2 - \nu_1 \quad (1)$$

$$B = (\nu_2 + \nu_3 - 3\nu_1)/15 \quad (2)$$

The nephelauxetic ratio¹⁶ β , Slater-Condon¹⁷ param-

eters F_2 and F_4 , Slater-Condon-Shortley¹⁷ parameters F^2 and F^4 , Dq/B , ν_3/ν_1 , ν_2/ν_1 , ν_3/ν_2 and f_L (crystal field parameter for ligand) values were also calculated (Table 3). The values of β (0.83–0.87), B (810–846), F_2 (1346–1407) and F_4 (107–112), F^2 (6.8×10^4) and F^4 (4.9×10^4), ν_3/ν_1 (2.3), ν_2/ν_1 (2.1), ν_3/ν_2 (1.1) and Dq/B (1.14–1.17) supports the octahedral geometry proposed for the Co^{II} complexes¹⁸.

We observed that the values of B (810–846) in the present complexes are less than the free cobalt(II) ion value (971 cm^{-1}). The reduction in B value on complexation is due to nephelauxetic effect which describes the

Table 3. Ligand field energy parameters data of Co^{II} complexes (cm⁻¹)

Complex	R	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	10Dq	B	β	F_2	F_4	F^2	F^4	ν_3/ν_1	ν_2/ν_1	ν_3/ν_2	Dq/B	f_L
CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-1)	H	8500	18000	20200	9500	846	0.8712	1407	112	68944	49424	2.37	2.11	1.11	1.12	0.94
CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-2)	3-CH ₃	8600	18200	20000	9600	840	0.8650	1395	111	68402	49035	2.32	2.11	1.09	1.14	0.95
CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-3)	4-CH ₃	8600	18300	20200	9700	846	0.8712	1406	112	68941	49424	2.34	2.12	1.10	1.14	0.95
CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-4)	5-CH ₃	8500	18100	20100	9600	846	0.8712	1407	112	68944	49424	2.36	2.12	1.11	1.33	0.94
CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-5)	5-Cl	8550	18100	19900	9550	823	0.8475	1368	109	67044	48062	2.32	2.11	1.09	1.15	0.95
CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-6)	5-Br	8650	18100	20000	9450	810	0.8340	1346	107	65958	47284	2.31	2.09	1.10	1.16	0.96
CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-7)	3-OCH ₃	8600	18200	19900	9600	820	0.8444	1362	108	66773	47868	2.31	2.11	1.09	1.17	0.95
CoL ₂ (Ligand : LH-8)	5 6	8500	18100	20100	9600	846	0.8712	1406	112	68894	49424	2.36	2.12	1.11	1.13	0.94

fact that B value decreases on complexation whereas free metal ion values are relatively high. Nephelauxetic effect is explained on the grounds of central field covalency and symmetry restricted covalency¹⁶. Thus we concluded that the Co^{II} complexes are covalent in nature. The values of f_L for the ligands lie in the range 0.94–0.96 and these values suggest that the ligands should be placed in between urea and ammonia in the spectrochemical series.

The IR spectra of the ligands and that of the Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes have been compared. Thiazole ring and phenyl ring vibrations occur at ~ 1600 m, ~ 1530 m, ~ 1480 m, ~ 1430 m cm^{-1} in the ligands and complexes (m indicates medium band). The ligands exhibit ν_{OH} , $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ modes at ~ 3400 (a broad and weak band due to phenolic -OH group suggesting an intramolecular hydrogen bonding between phenolic -OH group and azomethine nitrogen), ~ 1630 , ~ 1280 cm^{-1} respectively and these values are in accordance with the earlier reported data¹⁰. The absence of ν_{OH} mode in the complexes indicates the involvement of phenolic -OH group in metal-oxygen bond formation. The $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ modes in the complexes occur at ~ 1580 and ~ 1330 cm^{-1} respectively. The lowering of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and shifting of $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ towards higher frequency in complexes as compared to ligands indicate that coordination to the central metal takes place through oxygen of phenolic -OH group and nitrogen of azomethine group¹⁰. We proposed that the coordination to central metal atom takes place through oxygen of the phenolic -OH group, nitrogen of azomethine group¹⁰ and nitrogen of thiazole moiety¹⁹. Thus the ligands LH-1 to LH-8 behave as NNO donor ligands.

The magnetic moments of square planar, tetrahedral and octahedral complexes of Co^{II} lie in the range 2.0–2.2, 4.3–4.7 and 4.7–5.2 B.M.²⁰ respectively. Figgis and Nyhorne²¹ have shown that the most of the square planar complexes possess magnetic moment in the range 2.0–2.7 B.M. The values of magnetic moments (Table 2) of the present Co^{II} complexes lie in the range 4.8–5.2 B.M. These values support the octahedral geometry proposed for Co^{II} complexes²⁰. The Zn^{II} complexes are diamagnetic.

Literature survey reveals that Schiff bases and their complexes exhibit antibacterial, antifungal, anticancer and antitubercular activities²². In present studies we have tested the Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes for the evaluation of antibac-

terial activity against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Staphylococcus aureus* and antifungal activity against *A. niger* and *C. albicans* by serial dilution technique¹² in DMF in the concentration range 1–50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The MIC values have been reported. The MIC values of antibacterial activity of Co^{II} complexes lie in the range 8–12 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ as against 12–16 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for the parent ligands. The MIC values of antifungal activity of Co^{II} complexes lie in the range 6–8 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ as against 10–12 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for parent ligands. The MIC values of antibacterial activity of Zn^{II} complexes lie in the range 6–8 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and that of antifungal activity lie in the range 4–6 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. It is observed that the complexes exhibit pronounced antibacterial and antifungal activity as compared to the parent ligands. Enhanced activity of the metal complexes can be explained on the basis of Overtone's concept and chelation theory^{23,24}. According to Overtone's concept of cell permeability, the lipid membrane surrounding the cell favors the passage of only lipid soluble materials (which controls the microbial activity). Chelation reduces the polarity of the metal ion due to partial sharing of positive charge of metal ion with donor groups and also due to the delocalization of π electrons over whole chelate ring. Thus chelation increases the lipophilic character in the complexes and results in enhancement of activity. The increased lipophilic character enhances the penetration of the complexes into lipid membrane and blocks the metal binding sites on enzymes of microorganisms. The complexes disturb the respiration process of the cell and block the synthesis of proteins and therefore further growth of the microorganisms is restricted. The mode of action of compounds may involve hydrogen bonding through azomethine nitrogen with active centers of the cell constituents and causes interference with normal cell process.

Conclusion :

Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes are reddish brown and orange red colored crystalline solids respectively and possess 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry and an octahedral geometry. They are covalent in nature. The f_L values suggested that the ligands should be placed in between urea and ammonia in the spectrochemical series. The coordination takes place through oxygen of the phenolic -OH group, nitrogen of the azomethine group and nitrogen of the thiazole moiety. The ligands thus behave as tridentate with NNO donor set. The Zn^{II} and Co^{II} com-

plexes exhibit enhanced antibacterial and antifungal activity as compared to their parent ligands. The structure of the complexes is depicted in the Fig. 2.

Fig. 2

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solvents were purified according to standard procedures and distilled before use.

Synthesis of Schiff bases :

A solution of *o*-hydroxyaldehyde in ethanol was added to the ethanolic solution of 4-(*p*-fluorophenyl)-2-aminothiazole in equimolar amounts. The mixture was refluxed on water bath for 30 min. The Schiff base (LH-1 to LH-8) thus formed was filtered at suction, recrystallized from ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. The purity of the Schiff bases was tested by TLC.

Synthesis of Co^{II} complexes :

An ethanolic solution of cobalt acetate (0.01 *M*) was added to the ethanolic solution of 4-(*p*-fluorophenyl)-2-aminothiazole (0.02 *M*) and *o*-hydroxyaldehyde (0.02 *M*) or of Schiff base (0.02 *M*) (LH-1 to LH-8). The reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath for about one hour. On standing the shining reddish brown crystals of Co^{II} complex began to separate. The crystals separated were filtered, washed with hot ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Synthesis of Zn^{II} complexes :

An ethanolic solution of zinc acetate (0.01 *M*) was added to the ethanolic solution of 4-(*p*-fluorophenyl)-2-aminothiazole (0.02 *M*) and *o*-hydroxyaldehyde (0.02 *M*) or of Schiff base (0.02 *M*) (LH-1 to LH-8). The reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath for thirty minutes. The shining orange red colored crystals of zinc complex

were obtained. The crystals of the complex were filtered, washed with hot ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Physical measurements :

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses of the Schiff bases and the complexes were performed by conventional microanalytical techniques. Metal contents were determined by gravimetric methods. Molecular weights were determined by cryoscopic method. Ultraviolet and visible region spectra were recorded in chloroform solution on Shimadzu UV-Visible spectrophotometer using quartz cells at room temperature. Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr pellets on Perkin-Elmer 783 IR spectrophotometer in the range 4000–250 cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 on Varian 300 MHz spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard.

Antibacterial and antifungal activities were evaluated by serial dilution technique¹². The test organisms used were *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the authorities of Solapur University, Solapur and Shivaji University, Kolhapur for providing research facilities. One of the authors (ASL) is thankful to Mr. D. G. Kadam and Mrs. S. N. Deshpande for useful discussion.

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